

Speculation on Antiparticles From Special Relativity

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The notion of an antiparticle was developed by Dirac by linearizing the Klein-Gordon equation and retaining a $-E$ solution for a free particle. The Klein-Gordon equation follows from the special relativistic equation: $E^2 = p^2 + m^2 c^4$ ($c=1$) which may be derived by viewing a rest mass, m_0 , in a rest frame and comparing this scenario to one seen from a frame moving with constant $-v$ (velocity). In other words, this equation only makes sense if $m_0 > 0$, yet one may mathematically set $m_0 = 0$ and find that $E^2 = p^2$ or $E = pc$. (Interestingly, one may take Maxwell's equations which make sense for charge and current densities and set these to zero and still find a solution for the electric and magnetic fields. This solution is said to represent a photon.)

The equation $E = pc$ represents a photon, yet it is not clear why it should arise by setting $m_0 = 0$, unless there is in fact a physical manner in which one may actually eliminate rest mass. We suggest that if one considers a rest mass decaying into two photons, one does not have equivalence through time reversal. Thus, one might suggest mathematically the existence of a $-m_0$ or antiparticle such that one may have $-E$ which is not mathematically excluded from $E^2 = p^2 + m^2 c^4$. $-m_0$ is also not excluded. In other words, we suggest that it seems one should postulate the existence of an antiparticle from the fact that one obtains $E = pc$ from $E^2 = p^2 + m^2 c^4$ ($c=1$) and argues that one becomes the other if $m_0 = 0$. Otherwise, it seems that there is no physical reason for setting $m_0 = 0$ and no comparison of the two equations should be made.

Photon Relation $E = pc$

The photon relation $E = pc$ may be obtained in various ways. First, it may be considered an experimental observation and secondly, it follows from Maxwell's equations for E (electric field) and B (magnetic field) if one sets charge and current densities to zero (which seems like an unphysical thing to do). In such a case, one may define free energy and momentum densities as:

$$.5 \epsilon_0 E \cdot E + .5 / \mu_0 B \cdot B \quad ((1a)) \quad \text{and} \quad 1 / \mu_0 E \times B \quad ((1b))$$

and integrate over space. From Maxwell's equations, it is already known that E and B are perpendicular and are proportional to $\cos(-\omega t + kx)$.

A third way to obtain this relation is to use the continuity equation:

$$d/dt \text{ partial } \{ .5 \epsilon_0 E \cdot E + .5 / \mu_0 B \cdot B \} + \text{grad partial dot } 1 / \mu_0 E \times B = 0 \quad ((2))$$

$$\text{This suggests } E = A \cos(-\omega t + kx) \text{ and } B \text{ (perpendicular to } E) = A \cos(-\omega t + kx) \quad ((3))$$

Furthermore, frequency = speed/wavelength is known to hold for physical waves.

In short, $E=pc$ does not seem to explicitly rely on special relativity, although it may be noted that special relativistic transformations were obtained by Lorentz by insisting that Maxwell's equations remain invariant under a boost.

Derivation of $E^2 = p^2 + m^2 c^4$

If one assumes that a rest mass exists, then in the rest frame, one has $p=0$ and m_0 which may be considered proportional to a kind of energy. In a moving frame, one has momentum which is a kind of flux proportional to $m_0 v$ and possibly a new energy $E(m_0, v)$. In such a case, $p = E(m_0, v) \frac{v}{c}$.

If one considers a linear transformation, then:

$$\begin{pmatrix} p \\ E \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} A & v B(v) \\ C & B(v) \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ m_0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (4)$$

In principle, one does not know what to use for A and C a priori.

Then: $p = B v m_0$ and $E = B m_0$. If one considers that (p, E) and $(0, m_0)$ represent the same physical state simply viewed by moving frame in the first case, there should be an invariant such that all vectors are the same. A vector itself is not the same, but its magnitude may be. The problem is that $E(m_0, v) > m_0$ it seems, so one needs:

$$E^2 - p^2 = m_0^2 c^4 \quad \text{as a magnitude equation} \quad (5)$$

This leads to $B(v) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - v^2/b^2}}$, where b is a constant with units of speed.

Comparison of $E^2 = p^2 b^2 + m_0^2 c^4$ with $E=pc$

One may notice that if $m_0=0$, then $E^2 = p^2 b^2$ which is equivalent to $E=pc$ if $b=c$. Of course, setting $m_0=0$ seems to be completely unphysical and bypasses the derivation given above in which m_0 cannot be 0. Nevertheless, if one could somehow have rest mass disappear, one could still have a free energy and momentum satisfying $E=pc$. We argue that this suggests a physical process in nature in which this may occur.

It seems unlikely that an m_0 decay into two photons (momentum conservation) because of time reversal difficulties. This seems to lead to the notion of an m_0 and $-m_0$ which is not excluded by $E^2 = p^2 + m_0^2 c^4$.

If an m_0 and $-m_0$ were to combine and remove rest mass, the energy of each could be described by a photon with $E=pc$.

As a result, we suggest that by using $E^2 = p^2 + m_0^2 c^4$ and suggesting that $m_0=0$ leads to $E=pc$ is equivalent to postulating the idea of an antiparticle.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that even though the antiparticle was proposed by Dirac by considering a $-E$ free particle solution of a linearized differential equation compatible with the

Klein-Gordon equation, considering $E^2 = p^2 c^2 + m_0^2 c^4$ to be compatible with $E = pc$ for $m_0 = 0$ implies the same thing. $E^2 = p^2 c^2 + m_0^2 c^4$ should not have m_0 set to 0. Thus, if one does so, we suggest that this must be done for a physical reason, i.e. there must be a physical way for the mass to disappear without energy disappearing. We reject the decay of m_0 into two photons for time reversal reasons and so suggest an antiparticle $-m_0$. $E^2 = p^2 c^2 + m_0^2 c^4$ (c=1) does not exclude either $-E$ or $-m_0$, but it is the process of taking $E^2 = p^2 c^2 + m_0^2 c^4$ and setting $m_0 = 0$ to obtain the photon $E = pc$ equation which suggests the idea of an antiparticle and process which may remove rest mass.